

**WEB-BASED VEHICLE MONITORING SYSTEM OF MINDANAO STATE
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Web-Based Vehicle Monitoring System of Mindanao State University Lanao Del Norte Agricultural College

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Abstract

The paper presents the development and implementation of a Web-Based Vehicle Monitoring System at Mindanao State University-Lanao del Norte Agricultural College (MSU-LNAC). The current manual system, characterized by pen-and-logbook entries, is inefficient, prone to errors, and time-consuming. The proposed solution leverages QR code technology and SMS notifications to automate and streamline the monitoring process, enhancing both accuracy and efficiency. The system's development follows the Software Development Life Cycle (SDLC) using the waterfall model, ensuring a structured approach from requirement gathering to deployment. Key objectives include optimizing operations, improving data accuracy, reducing processing time, and enhancing security measures. The system's effectiveness and user satisfaction were evaluated through questionnaires, yielding high satisfaction scores among users. This research underscores the significance of integrating technology into campus security and administrative processes, offering a scalable solution for similar institutional environments. The study concludes with recommendations for future improvements, such as integrating the system with mobile platforms and enhancing database normalization and security features.

Keywords: *Web-Based System, Vehicle Monitoring System, QR Codes, SMS Notifications, SDLC*

Introduction

With the consistent advancements in technology, users are utilizing modern technology to streamline their work processes and increase efficiency thus, the role of computers in our daily lives is becoming increasingly significant (Roos, 2017). As educational institutions continue to grow, managing the entry and exit of vehicles on campus premises becomes increasingly important in various aspects, such as enabling the university to identify individuals entering and exiting the campus and enhance the safety and security of the campus premises. This necessity for efficient vehicle monitoring has led the researchers to propose a new emerging technology in MSU-LNAC. Currently, MSU-LNAC is still using logbook in recording the entry and exit of employees, students, and visitor. The researchers propose a new emerging technology that would be advantageous for the institution, specifically in improving the monitoring of vehicles' entry and exit in the campus.

The proposed system will also incorporate a visitor form page that requires visitors to fill out the form in order to generate the QR code and present it to the security guard assigned at the campus gate. Alongside this functionality, the methodology utilized by researchers in developing this system is the Software Development Life Cycle, employing the waterfall model approach.

Research Objectives

Based on the initial interview and observation of the researchers, the campus' existing operational structure mainly relies on manual techniques, notably pen and logbook, for monitoring vehicle entrances and exits. The following are the specific problems identified in this study:

1. The existing process is time-consuming. This is because unregistered vehicles especially the vehicles of the visitors are required to present their ID and respond to every security question.
2. Inaccurate data recording of vehicle information. This can occur due to illegible handwriting, incomplete entries, and the absence of restrictions, such as failing to adhere to standard formatting requirements. For example, the 11-digit format for cellphone numbers, plate numbers, and other important data.
3. Delays in providing reports are due to manual records. Because information stored across multiple manual records or documents, it requires time for consolidation.
4. Paper-based documentation in manual systems of vehicle is vulnerable to loss, damage, or deterioration over time. This poses a risk of data loss and can make it challenging to retrieve critical information when needed.

Methodology

In this study, meticulous attention was given to every aspect of the research process to ensure the collection of relevant and insightful information essential for achieving the study's objectives. Recognizing the significance of a structured approach in software development, the researchers chose to use the Software Development Life Cycle (SDLC) framework, specifically utilizing for the approach of Waterfall Model.

This model, renowned for its sequential and phased approach, encompasses seven pivotal stages: requirement analysis, planning, design, development, testing and evaluation, deployment, and maintenance. Each of these phases was meticulously followed to ensure

a methodical and efficient development process for the proposed system. By adhering to these established procedures, the researchers aimed to achieve not only the desired functionality but also reliability and scalability in the final system product.

Figure 1. *Software Development Life Cycle (SDLC)-Waterfall Model*

The researcher used the SDLC-Waterfall Model for this study due to its structured and sequential nature, which allows for a clear and concise approach to software development. The Waterfall Model is a linear, sequential approach to the software development lifecycle (SDLC) that is popular in software engineering and product development. Mohamed (2018) emphasizes that the Waterfall Model is a traditional software development process model that has been widely used and is considered the most popular SDLC model. This model is characterized by dividing the process of software development into separate phases which move in a linear progression, similar to a waterfall.

In this study, the Waterfall Model of the Software Development Life Cycle (SDLC) was utilized to ensure a systematic and structured approach to the development of the web-based vehicle monitoring system. By completing each phase before moving on to the next, we ensured that all possible requirements were thoroughly captured and documented. This meticulous approach allowed us to define a robust system design and architecture, leading to a reliable development and testing process that verified the system's functionality. The deployment phase followed, where the system was implemented and maintained with ongoing technical support for users. The Waterfall Model was particularly advantageous for our project as it allowed us to freeze the scope of each phase before progressing, providing clear documentation and making the model easy to implement regardless of the project's size. Testing at every stage further guaranteed that the system met all specified requirements, resulting in a comprehensive and reliable solution.

Requirements Analysis

System requirements analysis is a critical phase in the software development lifecycle. System requirements is a statement that identifies the functionality that is needed by a system in order to satisfy the customer's requirements (Siedle, 2015). Requirements analysis focuses on the tasks that determine the needs or conditions to meet the new or altered product or project, taking account of the possibly conflicting requirements of the various stakeholders.

During the requirements analysis phase, the researcher conducted consultations and interviews with stakeholders to gather and analyze requirements needed. One-on-one interview was the technique used for gathering requirements. This was fully planned and prepared to ensure that stakeholders can provide the most valuable input. The interviews and consultations conducted for this study were specifically with the security guards assigned at the entrance and exit gates of the campus, as they were directly involved in the system being developed. The researchers also gathered the acquisition of sample forms of vehicles monitoring systems to further analyze and

help the existing process.

The goal of requirements analysis is to understand the requirements, study and analyze the system, discuss with the users, and perform task analysis to bring out the essential features of the study. The analysis phase is critical for reviewing the efficiency, effectiveness, relevance, and sustainability of the proposed system, and for documenting results and measuring the impact of the system in relation to the overall objectives.

Planning

In this phase, the researcher started planning, which is key to success their goals. They carefully set objectives, plans, and tools needed for their work. They gave close attention to efficiency, clarity, and alignment in every aspect. This involves setting goals, allocating resources, and scheduling tasks. Good planning in this stage helps to bring structure, vision, and adaptability, ensuring that decisions and actions are well-thought-out. It lays the groundwork for success, paving the way for progress in this research.

The roles and responsibilities of each researcher involved in the project were clearly defined. The first researcher was responsible for programming the system and preparing the manuscript, which involves designing, implementing, and testing the system, as well as documenting the development process and findings in the manuscript. The second researcher conducted research to gather pertinent information that can aid the project by looking for studies, books, and other resources to offer insights and support the project's goals. The third researcher contacted the school to request the required paperwork, including approval forms, consent forms, and other necessary documentation for the project, ensuring that all signatures and approvals are collected. Each researcher contributed significantly to the project's success with their knowledge and abilities. With the shared duties, team members moved the project forward quickly and successfully.

During the scheduling phase of planning, an essential stage in every project's duration, researchers used Gantt charts (see Appendix A) as a tool to visualize project tasks, timeframes, and dependencies. The dynamic features and easy-to-understand format of Gantt charts facilitate effective resource allocation, milestone identification, and progress tracking throughout the project.

Resource allocation in the project ensures that the system is developed with robust back-end hardware requirements for smooth functioning. Researchers of this study allocated a computer server with specifications that include a Core i3 processor, 8GB of RAM, and Windows 10. This allocation provided sufficient processing and storage power for efficient system operation. There was the integration of Twilio API for communication, MySQL Database for data storage, Xampp for local server deployment, PHP for web development, and network connectivity through WIFI infrastructure or cellular data which were all essential components.

Meeting planning, regular weekly project status meetings, online updates, instant messaging for brief exchanges, and document sharing were conducted as part of the communication strategy. A formal project sign-off at the end of each step was also implemented leading to the project's completion and final approval. Throughout the entire development lifecycle, these organized procedures promoted an efficient cooperation, progress tracking, and quality control.

System Design

System design helps in specifying hardware and system requirements and also helps in defining overall system architecture. The Web-Based Vehicle Monitoring System of Mindanao State University Lanao del Norte Agricultural College is composed of six comprehensive diagrams meticulously designed by the researchers. These diagrams include a System Flow Chart that outlines the data and logic flow within the system, a Use Case Diagram that shows interactions between actors and the system, and an Entity Relationship Diagram (ERD) that illustrates the links between various data entities. The system architecture diagram gives an overview of the system's structure. Finally, a structured representation of the system's modules and operations is shown in a Hierarchical Input Process Output Diagram. With their combination, the diagrams provided a thorough understanding of the architecture, functionality, and parts of the system, which made the designing, building, and documenting the system easier.

Development

During the development phase of the system, it begun with the creating Graphical User Interface (GUI) this was the visual part of the application that users interact with. It was designed to be user-friendly, intuitive, and visually appealing. In this context, GUI was created using a combination of HTML, CSS, and JavaScript to design and layout elements like buttons, forms, menus, etc., on web pages.

Hypertext Preprocessor (PHP) was also used by the researchers. PHP is a server-side scripting language used for web development. It is commonly used to generate dynamic web page content, interact with databases, handle forms, manage sessions, and perform various other server-side tasks.

Cascading Style Sheets (CSS) was used to style the HTML elements created in the GUI. It defines how elements are displayed on the screen, including layout, colors, fonts, and other visual aspects. CSS ensures consistency and enhances the visual appeal of the user interface.

JavaScript is a client-side scripting language that adds interactivity and dynamic behavior to web pages. The researcher used this in

this study to create features like form validation, animations, dynamic content updates, and more. JavaScript enhances user experience by making web applications more responsive and interactive.

MySQL Database is a popular open-source relational database management system. It was used as the backend database to store and manage data for the application. PHP scripts interact with the MySQL database to retrieve, insert, update, and delete data as needed.

Twilio API is a cloud communications platform that provides APIs for developers to integrate SMS, and other communication features into their applications. In this case, the Twilio API was used to enable functionalities such as SMS messaging and two-factor authentication, enhancing the security and communication capabilities of the system.

Domain Hosting services provided the infrastructure and resources needed to host the web application on the internet. This allows users to access the system using a domain name.

Hardware Scanner is used as part of the system implementation. It allows users to scan QR codes, presumably to access certain functionalities or data within the application. The hardware scanner is connected to a personal computer or laptop, which serves as the interface for interacting with the scanner.

Admin users of the system require personal computers or laptops to operate the full system. These devices are used to access the system's backend interface, manage user accounts, configure settings, view reports, and perform other administrative tasks.

Testing and Evaluation

The MSU-LNAC Web-based Vehicle Monitoring System underwent comprehensive evaluation through the use of both black box and white box testing methodologies. Black box testing (user) was employed to assess the system's functionality and usability from a user-centric standpoint, without delving into its internal structure or code. This approach allowed researchers to simulate end-user interactions, validating system requirements, and verifying integration with external services such as QR code scanning and SMS notifications. Conversely, white box testing (developer) involves examining the system's internal structure and code to ensure correctness and efficiency. By scrutinizing the underlying logic and functionality, white box testing validated the internal workings of the system and addresses any potential issues or inefficiencies in its implementation. Together, these testing methodologies ensured that the MSU-LNAC vehicle monitoring system met functional and non-functional requirements while maintaining correctness and efficiency in its operation.

Respondents

The researchers used Purposive Sampling Techniques to identify the participants chosen from each user group of the Web-Based Vehicle Monitoring System, including administrators, security guards, students, employee, other members of the academic community, and visitors. Intentionally, this selection was made to collect a range of viewpoints regarding the functionality and usability and satisfaction of the system.

This decision was guided by the need to gather targeted and meaningful data that directly address the research questions and objectives. Each respondent was carefully chosen based on their relevance to the research focus, with considerations given to factors such as expertise, diversity, and representation of key groups. The researchers used an approach called the 'Rule of Thumb,' which suggests that the sample size should be a minimum of 10% of the population or 30 for smaller populations. In this study, the respondents were coming from employees, students, and the community, with a population of 10 being equally divided.

The main consideration in the purposive sampling was that respondents should be exclusively employees, students, of MSU-LNAC and community members of Ragain, SND who own vehicles, regardless of gender. Excluded from the sampling are employees, students, and community members of Ragain SND who do not own vehicles.

Instrument

The researchers assessed the system's functionality, usability and user interface satisfaction by employing a modified version of CSUQ and USE. These questionnaires were adapted and modified to evaluate the MSU-LNAC web-based vehicle monitoring system. The survey method was utilized by the researchers to gather, analyze, and interpret data derived from the responses of the system's users. Through this approach, the researchers aimed to comprehensively evaluate the system's functionality, usability and user satisfaction, allowing for insights into areas of improvement and optimization for enhancing user experience and system effectiveness.

Procedure

In this phase, the researchers used a checklist Questionnaire as their primary instrument. The questionnaire contained a list of all the functions of the system that will be tested and evaluated by end-users. To gather feedback, a rating system with 5 Point Likert Scale was included in the evaluation.

In order to ensure the validity and reliability of responses, the researcher facilitated the actual administration of the questionnaire. In the administration of the questionnaire, the researcher provided a brief orientation to the respondent regarding how to answer the distributed questionnaire. After gathering the data, Microsoft Office Excel will be employed to record process the data.

Table 1. *Likert Scale of the Evaluation Questionnaire*

<i>Weight</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
5	Strongly Agree
4	Agree
3	Neither Agree Or Disagree
2	Disagree
1	Strongly Disagree

Table 1 illustrates how respondents' levels of agreement ranging from strongly agree to strongly disagree. This determines the reference point for each verbal interpretation in relation to the proposed system.

Data Analysis

After testing and evaluation, the researchers analyzed and interpret the data using statistical tool that includes weighted mean, frequency, and percentage to calculate and analyze the data collected while the designed system was being tested.

Weighted Mean. Using this statistical method, the mean end user rating for each system's functioning will be ascertained. multiplying the weight (or potential) of a certain event or result by the quantitative result that goes along with it, and then adding up all the results.

Frequency and Percentage. Using the statistical method, the researchers can determined the average end user rating for each system's functioning. They first multiply the frequency by 100 and divided it by the total number of results. This process helped the researcher understand how often each rating occurs and what proportion it represents out of the total.

Verbal Interpretation. The Likert scale utilized in the study employs a five-point system to gauge respondent opinions, ranging from "Strongly Disagree" to "Strongly Agree." These points correspond to numerical scores from 1 to 5, allowing for nuanced interpretation of participant perspectives. Specific intervals within this range aid in analyzing responses, guiding researchers in extracting detailed insights from collected data.

The purpose of establishing these intervals was to facilitate understanding and analysis of respondents' opinions. By defining distinct ranges based on the Likert scale scores, researchers categorized participant responses and draw meaningful conclusions about system functionality, usability and user satisfaction.

This method ensured a systematic approach to interpreting evaluation data, enhancing the depth and accuracy of analysis.

Table 2. *Weight, Mean Range and Verbal Interpretation of the Study*

<i>Weight/Scale</i>	<i>Mean Range</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
1	1.00 – 1.8	Strongly Disagree
2	1.9 - 2.60	Disagree
3	2.7 – 3.4	Neither Agree Or Disagree
4	3.5 – 4.2	Agree
5	4.3 – 5.00	Strongly Agree

Respondents expressed their degree of agreement or disagreement with the statements using the scale that was used in the questionnaire by using explicit verbal interpretations. A score of one (1) denotes a strongly disagreement, meaning the respondent genuinely disagrees with the statement. A score of two (2) on the scale denotes disagreement, but not to the same extent as the preceding option. A score of three (3) conveys a neutral attitude and implies ambiguity or disinterest regarding the assertion. On the other hand, a score of (4) denotes agreement, if not perfect agreement, and a score of five (5) denotes strong agreement, suggesting a strong belief in the veracity of the assertion. Respondents were able to articulate their viewpoints clearly by using this scale, which made it easier in the gathering of complex and insightful data for analysis.

Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the findings and analysis derived from the respondents' analyzed data, which were used to assess the functionality, usability, and satisfaction of the system using the QUIS and USE evaluation questionnaires. Additionally, the researcher provided a graphical description of the system illustrating its processes to demonstrate its logical nature.

Requirements Specification

Mindanao State University Lanao del Norte Agricultural College is the proponent of the researchers where the system will be implemented. This study will focus on the following areas, both functional and non-functional requirements:

Functional

Functional requirements for the MSU-LNAC web-based vehicle monitoring system, such as the following:

New Vehicle Registration and Management

The system allows administrators to register and manage driver profiles and vehicle information. The system generates stickers containing QR codes for registered communities, employees, and students.

Security and Notification System

The system allows text notifications to be sent to concerned personnel upon scanning a QR code using the hardware QR code scanner before allowing vehicle entry or exit. The system automatically records the date and time of driver entry and exit from the campus.

User Access and Authorization

The system grants access to security guards, administrators, or assigned personnel designated by the institution. The system restricts system administrators from deleting or updating records without the authorization of the vehicle owner.

Visitor Management

The system requires visitors to register online through the system's website URL, providing a convenient and centralized platform for managing visitor entries and ensuring that all necessary information is captured accurately and securely.

System Dependency

The system depends on an internet connection for optimal functionality, ensuring real-time data synchronization and seamless communication between the various components of the web-based vehicle monitoring system.

Reporting and Data Management

The system maintains summary reports, exclusively accessible to administrators, for viewing collected data. In addition to maintaining summary reports accessible to administrators, the system also fulfills the Visitor Management requirement by providing a streamlined process for registering and monitoring visitors entering the campus. Through the integration of QR codes and SMS notifications, administrators can efficiently monitor visitor movements, ensuring enhanced security and accountability while facilitating a smooth visitor experience.

Non-Functional

Operational

This system utilizes a 2D wireless hardware scanner to scan the QR code used by the security guard, enhancing efficiency and accuracy in the scanning process. This system uses a system unit/laptop with a minimum spec of Core i3 as a server unit. This system runs online and offline. When online, it uses Wi-Fi or cellular data with a minimum of 2.4 GHz, and when offline, it uses localhost. This QR code scanner module may open on any Android phone as long as it has a browser, or on a laptop with any browser installed.

Performance

This system updates consistently if someone is entering or leaving the campus. This system scans QR code in 5-10 seconds. It displays the summary regularly based on your needs. It sends consistently a message via text before entering /leaving the campus. Further, this supports more than one user: two security guards for entry and exit, and one administrator.

Security

Access to the database is exclusive only to the administrator assigned by the institution. The administrator and security guard accounts are protected by a username and password. The system unit used as a server is also protected by a password and username to ensure that no one can access it.

System Design

In this phase, it illustrates the system's structure and functionality to achieve its goals. Researchers employed system design to represent the logical nature of the system—its tasks—without specifying how, where, or by whom they are accomplished, and how the process unfolds. To depict the logical system design, researchers utilized various diagrams.

Entity Relationship Diagram (ERD)

The Entity Relationship Diagram shown in Figure 2 depicts the relationships between entities, attributes, and relationships. It illustrates the role of each entity as well as the connections between them. It represents a database intended to hold all transactional and reference data of the system.

The relationships among the various actors, such as the designation list, owner list, vehicle list, gate pass, security guard list, message, admin list, daily logs, and summary list, are best depicted in this Entity-Relationship Diagram (ERD).

The relationship between the designation list and owner list is one-to-one, indicating that each owner corresponds to only one designation (student, employee, community member, or visitor). Conversely, the relationship from the owner list to the vehicle list is one-to-many, signifying that an owner can possess more than one vehicle. Similarly, the relationship between the vehicle list and gate pass is one-to-one, meaning that each vehicle can only obtain one QR code.

On the other hand, the relationship between the gate pass and security guard is one-to-many, allowing a security guard to scan multiple QR codes. The relationship between the security guard list and messages is one-to-one, indicating that if a guard scans a registered QR code, the system will dispatch one message for each scan.

Conversely, the relationship between messages and the admin list is many-to-one, indicating that only one admin can receive messages from the system when scanning QR codes. Furthermore, the relationship between the admin list and daily logs is one-to-one, meaning that every admin who receives a message triggers the system to store data on vehicles entering or leaving the campus.

Lastly, the relationship between daily logs and summary logs is one-to-many, implying that summary logs compile all the entries from the daily logs.

Figure 2. Entity Relationship Diagram of MSU-LNAC Web-Based Vehicle Monitoring System

System Flow Chart

Figure 3. System Flow Chart of MSU-LNAC Web-Based Vehicle Monitoring System

Figure 3 outlines a process for managing visitor information through a website interface. This is the flow that the end user follows in using the system.

Initially, users start by entering the website via a browser and inputting their username and password. The system then verifies if the account belongs to a valid Security Guard (SG) or admin. If the credentials are invalid, the user is redirected to login page to login again. Valid accounts grant access to different functionalities based on the user's role.

Admins can open the Admin Dashboard to input Security Guard information, which is subsequently stored in the database. Records are generated from this stored information. Admins can also input vehicle information and generate a QR code for the vehicle.

On the other hand, Security Guards can access the Scanner Interface to scan QR codes from vehicles owner or visitor. The system checks if the scanned QR code matches existing records. If a match is found, the details and records are displayed, and an SMS notification is sent. If no match is found, the process ends.

Visitors to the website are required to fill out a form, after which a QR code is generated for them.

System Architecture Diagram

The system architecture diagram shows in Figure 4 outlines the interaction flow among various components of the MSU-LNAC Web-Based Vehicle Monitoring System. It has been meticulously designed to accommodate diverse vehicle types and cater to registered members.

At its core, the system seamlessly integrates technology components to ensure efficient monitoring and management. Key nodes include the vehicle, Hardware QR code scanner, API gateway, server database, and client interface (computer).

Each registered vehicle is assigned a unique QR code as its digital identifier for campus entry and exit. Security guards utilize Hardware QR code scanners to capture vehicle information at the gate, subsequently sending the data to the database and triggering an SMS notification to the assigned personnel indicating entry or exit.

The server database securely stores data from the process, enabling comprehensive retrieval and analysis. Administrators access the client interface via a computer to oversee and manage the system effectively.

Through seamless interaction among nodes, the system ensures optimal functionality and performance in monitoring and managing vehicle movements at the MSU-LNAC campus.

Figure 4. System Architecture Diagram of MSU-LNAC Web-Based Vehicle Monitoring System

Hierarchical Input Process Output (HIPO) Diagram

HIPO Diagram evaluates the system and helps with documentation. It sets up a hierarchy among the software system's modules. Figure 5 provides a comprehensive visual representation of the HIPO diagram, which serves to elucidate the intricate composition and operational dynamics of a vehicle monitoring system. This diagram offers a structured breakdown of the system's components, functions, and their interrelations, facilitating a clear understanding of how the system operates.

It starts with authentication, which checks user credentials before granting access. After that, the Scanner component gathers vehicle data and presents it via an easy-to-use interface. Users may browse and manage an extensive list of registered vehicles using the Vehicle List function, and they can export data to Excel for additional analysis. Gate Pass Logs are used to carefully document daily actions and generate summarized reports that may be easily exported to Excel. With the help of a search function, the Report Record functionality makes it possible to generate comprehensive records and to efficiently retrieve information. Tools for keeping an up-to-date owner list, adding or removing users, changing data, and creating QR codes for quick identification are all provided by gate pass record management.

Lastly, the Member module offers administration features including handling user resets and deletions, adding new users, and maintaining member lists. When combined, these elements improve security and operational efficiency by ensuring the seamless functioning and efficient administration of the Vehicle Monitoring System.

Figure 5. HIPO Diagram of MSU-LNAC Web-Based Vehicle Monitoring System

Use Case Diagram

The use-case diagram depicted in Figure 6 provides an overview of the system's scope and user interactions. It illustrates the relationships between the actors and the various use cases within the system.

Figure 6. Use Case of MSU-LNAC Web-Based Vehicle Monitoring System

Use-case diagrams portray how actors interact with the system and its functionalities, elucidating the system's usage from a user perspective. However, they do not delve into the internal workings of the system. The campus designates specific actor to serve as system administrators. In this capacity, administrators possess full control over the system, the admin will login first with the username and password to open the system dashboard enabling them to perform tasks such as managing users, adding Security Guard accounts, managing reports, and registering students, employees, and community members.

Security guards also play a crucial role as actors within the system. They have the capability to log in and access the scanner interface, allowing them to scan QR codes.

Also, visitors represent another category of actors within the system. Visitors have the ability to fill out visitor forms, though with limited functionality compared to administrators and security guards.

Development

Figure 7 shows a screenshot of the main Login of the system. It includes the admin login form, visitor form, and scanner for authorized security guards.

Figure 7. Login Page of MSU-LNAC Web-Based Vehicle Monitoring System

Figure 8 shows the screenshot of the system dashboard that can only be accessed by the admin user where he/she is the only one who will manage the whole system.

Figure 8. Screenshot of the Dashboard of the Web Page of the MSU-LNAC Web- Based Vehicle Monitoring System

Figure 9 shows the screenshot of the vehicle list and the owner list of the vehicle where you can click the different button. The list of recorded vehicle owners has seven buttons: to click such as add register, export to excel, update, information, receipt of the QR code,

and delete button while the vehicle list has two buttons: exports to excel and update information.

Figure 9. List of Records Vehicle Owner and Vehicle List of the MSU-LNAC Web-Based Vehicle Monitoring System

Figure 10 below shows the screenshot of the summary logs of the vehicle entering and leaving the campus. The summary logs are the overall logs of entry and exit of the vehicle on campus, you can view all the summary logs of your desired information that you want to find in the summary logs.

Figure 10. Screenshots of the All Summary Logs of MSU-LNAC Web-Based Vehicle Monitoring System

Shown in figure 11 is the screenshot of the daily logs of the vehicle entering and leaving the campus. The daily logs are the daily

monitoring of vehicle entry and exit in the campus which you can only see on that day.

Figure 11. Screenshots of the Daily Logs of MSU-LNAC Web-Based Vehicle Monitoring System

Figure 12 shows the screenshot of the registration form for the Security guard. That contains their full name, username, and password. This security guard is a staff who are authorized to manage the Scanner to scan the QR Code in the gate.

Figure 12. Screenshot of the Security Guard registration Form of the MSU-LNAC Web-Based Vehicle Monitoring System

Shown in figure 13 is a screenshot of staff records, including the Security Guards who are authorized to handle the Scanner. This figure also illustrates where you can add another staff, delete staff, update staff information, and reset.

Figure 13. Screenshot of the Staff Records of the MSU-LNAC Web-Based Vehicle Monitoring System

Figure 14 shows the screenshots of updating a user by clicking the "Update" button in the staff records. This interface allows administrators to efficiently modify staff details, ensuring all relevant information is accurate and up-to-date.

Figure 14. Screenshots of the Update User /Staff Records of the MSU-LNAC Web-Based Vehicle Monitoring System

Figure 15 shows the screenshots of deleting a user when clicking the "Delete" button in the staff records. This feature enables administrators to remove staff details efficiently, ensuring that the records are current and only include active personnel.

Figure 15. Screenshots of the Delete User /Staff Records of the MSU-LNAC Web-Based Vehicle Monitoring System

Figure 16 shows screenshots when you click the buttons for updating records in the list of vehicle owners, where only the admin can manage it. This feature ensures that only authorized personnel can modify vehicle owner information, maintaining the security and integrity of the data.

Figure 16. Screenshots of the Update Information of List Records of Vehicle Owner of the MSU-LNAC Web-Based Vehicle Monitoring System

Depicted in Figure 17 are screenshots when you click the buttons for viewing information records in the list of vehicle owners, where only the admin can manage it. This feature allows administrators to easily access and review detailed vehicle owner information, ensuring effective oversight and management of the records.

Figure 17 Screenshots of the viewing Records Information in the List Records of Vehicle Owner of the MSU-LNAC Web-Based VMS

Figure 18 shows screenshots when you click the buttons for gate pass receipts in the list of vehicle owners, where only the admin can manage it. This functionality enables administrators to generate and manage gate pass receipts efficiently, providing a secure and controlled process for vehicle access and monitoring within the system.

Figure 18. Screenshots of Gate Pass receipt of List Records of Vehicle Owner of the MSU-LNAC Web-Based Vehicle Monitoring System

Depicted in figure 19 is a screenshot when you click the Reports Record buttons where you can search from a certain date to up to date and generate the result collected information of the vehicle owner where only the admin can manage it.

Figure 19. Screenshots of Research Result in the Report Record of Vehicle Owner of the MSU-LNAC Web-Based Vehicle Monitoring System

Figure 20 shows the screenshot of the registration form for employees, students, and community members who have their own vehicles and use them daily at the MSU-LNAC campus. The form contains personal information of the owner and vehicle details required for registration in the system.

Figure 20. Screenshots of the Registration form for Employee, Student, Community of the MSU-LNAC Web-Based Vehicle Monitoring System

Shown in figure 21 is the screenshot of the registration form for visitors. Visitors are required to fill out the form before submitting it.

Figure 21. Screenshots of the Visitor Registration of the MSU-LNAC Web-Based Vehicle Monitoring System

Figure 22 presents the screenshot of the system response and generating QR code. After visitor submit the registration. The system will respond, confirming that your information has been successfully registered. At this point, you can generate your QR code.

Figure 22. Screenshots of the System Response and Generating QR Code of the MSU-LNAC Web-Based Vehicle Monitoring System

Figure 23 shows below the screenshot of the scanner interface and the response of the system after scanning the QR code provided by the admin. This integration of QR code scanning functionality enhances security and efficiency in vehicle monitoring by swiftly verifying and processing vehicle entry and exit information.

Figure 23. Screenshots of the Scanner Interface and System Response to Scanned QR Code of the MSU-LNAC Web-Based Vehicle Monitoring System

Shown in Figure 24 is the screenshot of the downloaded file containing all summary logs in Excel format. This comprehensive summary includes vehicle entry and exit data, providing administrators with a detailed overview of campus traffic for effective monitoring and analysis.

Figure 24. Screenshots of Downloaded Summary logs in excel of the MSU-LNAC Web-Based Vehicle Monitoring System

Figure 25 displays the screenshot of the SMS notification message received by the admin when the system responds to the scanner scanning the QR code of a specific member. This feature ensures immediate notification to relevant personnel, enhancing real-time monitoring and management of vehicle access within the system.

Figure 25. Screenshots of a received message of admin from the system of the MSU-LNAC Web-Based Vehicle Monitoring System

Testing and Evaluation

Utilizing a survey questionnaire, crucial data has been gathered regarding various aspects of the system's performance and user experience. This questionnaire served as a structured tool to collect feedback from users across key areas, including security, ease of use, ease of learning, and user satisfaction. By distributing the questionnaire to a representative sample of users, diverse perspectives on the ease of use and ease of learning of the system were obtained. Through this evaluation, insights into the effectiveness of security measures, the ease of use and ease of learning, and overall user satisfaction have been gained. Furthermore, the researcher has calculated the weighted mean of every questionnaire to determine the survey results, which will aid in understanding the outcome of the evaluation process. These findings, along with the calculated results, have informed decisions on areas for improvement and optimization, enhancing the system's quality and user experience. The researcher appreciates the participation of users in this evaluation process, as it has been instrumental in tailoring the system to better meet their needs and expectations, the following tables are the results of testing and evaluation of the system.

Table 3 represents the respondents' answers regarding the security of the developed system. It illustrates how users perceive and test the system's security, especially in terms of securing the data collected by the system.

The table displays the weighted mean of each question. Question 1, 2 and 3 fall into the category of "Strongly agree," Based on the survey results, it indicates an average weighted mean of 4.9, signifying that the end-user agrees with the security of the system.

Table 3. Evaluation of the Security of the System (n=30)

Indicators	WM	Interpretation
Question 1	4.9	Strongly Agree
Question 2	4.93	Strongly Agree
Question 3	4.87	Strongly Agree
Average Weighted Mean	4.9	Agree

Table 4. Evaluation of the Ease of Use of the system (n=30)

Indicators	WM	Interpretation
Question 4	4.93	Strongly Agree
Question 5	4.99	Strongly Agree

Question 6	4.93	Strongly Agree
Question 7	4.93	Strongly Agree
Question 8	4.97	Strongly Agree
Average Weighted Mean	4.95	Strongly Agree

The table 4 presents the answer of the respondent with regard to the ease of use and ease of learning of the developed system. This shows how the user views and tries the system’s ease of ease of use of the system if it’s easy to use and.

The table shows the weighted mean of each question that respondents answered question 4, 5,6,7 and 8 falls right into the category of “Strongly Agree”. Based on the result of the survey, it shows an average weighted mean of 4.95 which means the end users strongly agree with the ease of use and ease of learning of the system.

Table 5 illustrates respondents' perceptions regarding the Ease of Learning of the developed system. It provides insights into how users perceive the system's ease of learning. The table displays the weighted mean for each question answered by respondents, specifically questions 9, 10, 11, and 12, all of which fall under the "Strongly Agree". According to the survey results, the average weighted mean is 4.93, indicating that end users strongly agree with the system's ease of learnability.

Table 5. Evaluation of the Ease of Learning of the system (n=30)

Indicators	WM	Interpretation
Question 9	4.93	Strongly Agree
Question 10	4.93	Strongly Agree
Question 11	4.90	Strongly Agree
Question 12	4.97	Strongly Agree
Average Weighted Mean	4.93	Strongly Agree

The table 6 presents the answers of the respondent with regard to the Satisfaction to the developed system. This shows users try the system’s and their satisfaction with the system if they are Satisfied with the system.

The table shows the weighted mean of each question that respondents answered question 13,15, and 16 falls right into the category of “Strongly Agree” while 14 falls right into the category of “Agree”. Based on the result of the survey, it shows an average weighted mean of 4.95 which means the end users strongly agree with the Satisfaction of the system.

Table 6. Evaluation of the Satisfaction of the System (n=30)

Indicators	WM	Interpretation
Question 13	4.97	Strongly Agree
Question 14	4.9	Strongly Agree
Question 15	4.97	Strongly Agree
Question 16	4.97	Strongly Agree
Average Weighted Mean	4.95	Strongly Agree

Frequency and Percentage

Based on the results of the overall survey conducted among 30 respondents using the questionnaires, the frequency and percentage distributions reveal valuable insights. Based on the results of the overall survey, the most prominent ratings came from the scale 5, with a frequency of 28.06 over 30 respondents and a corresponding percentage of 94%. This high rating indicates significant satisfaction among the participants. Following this, the scale 4 received a smaller frequency of 1.94, representing 6% of the respondents. Notably, there were no ratings of 3, 2, or 1, showing that there was not a single expression of dissatisfaction among the participants.

This overall rating from 30 respondent illustrate the overwhelmingly positive perception of the survey among the respondents. Overall, the majority of respondents expressed high satisfaction towards to the systems.

Table 7. Overall Frequency and Percentage Results (n=30)

Question	Frequency					Percentage				
	5	4	3	2	1	5	4	3	2	1
Q1	27	3	0	0	0	90%	10%	0	0	0
Q2	28	2	0	0	0	93%	7%	0	0	0
Q3	26	4	0	0	0	87%	13%	0	0	0
Q4	28	2	0	0	0	93%	7%	0	0	0
Q5	29	1	0	0	0	97%	3%	0	0	0
Q6	28	2	0	0	0	93%	7%	0	0	0
Q7	28	2	0	0	0	93%	7%	0	0	0
Q8	29	1	0	0	0	97%	3%	0	0	0
Q9	28	2	0	0	0	93%	7%	0	0	0
Q10	28	2	0	0	0	93%	7%	0	0	0
Q11	27	3	0	0	0	90%	10%	0	0	0
Q12	29	1	0	0	0	97%	3%	0	0	0

Q13	29	1	0	0	0	97%	3%	0	0	0
Q14	27	3	0	0	0	90%	10%	0	0	0
Q15	29	1	0	0	0	97%	3%	0	0	0
Q16	29	1	0	0	0	97%	3%	0	0	0
Total	28.1	1.94	0	0	0	94%	6%	0	0	0

The overall result from the user-respondents is shown in Figure 4.25. The survey has four categories: security, ease of use, ease of learn, and satisfaction. Each part got a score called an average weighted mean. Security got 4.90, which means people feel pretty safe using it. Ease of use got 4.95, showing that most people found it really simple to operate. Ease of learning got 4.93, indicating that it was not too hard for people to pick up how to use it. Lastly, satisfaction also got 4.93, suggesting that overall, people are quite happy with it. With the average scores from the four categories of 4.93, it implies that, on average, people are really satisfied with it.

Table 8 displays the performance and system capabilities of the system. The responder rates indicate that a 4.50 average weighted mean corresponds to users strongly agreeing with the system's performance and capabilities. This high rating suggests that users are highly satisfied with the performance and the capabilities of the system.

Table 8. Admin Evaluation of Performance/System Capabilities of the System

Indicators	WM	Interpretation
Question 1	5.00	Strongly Agree
Question 2	4.00	Agree
Average Weighted Mean	4.50	Strongly Agree

Table 9 displays respondents' perceptions of the security of the developed system. It presents the weighted mean of responses to questions in questionnaires 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, and 8, all falling under the category of "Strongly Agree." The survey results indicate an average weighted mean of 5, suggesting that end users strongly agree the security performance of the system.

Table 9. Admin Evaluation of Security of the System

Indicators	WM	Interpretation
Question 3	5.00	Strongly Agree
Question 4	5.00	Strongly Agree
Question 5	5.00	Strongly Agree
Question 6	5.00	Strongly Agree
Question 7	5.00	Strongly Agree
Question 8	5.00	Strongly Agree
Average Weighted Mean	5.00	Strongly Agree

Table 10 presents respondents' evaluations of the interface of the developed system. It displays the weighted mean of responses to questions 9, 10, 11, and 12 in questionnaires which all falling under the category of "Strongly Agree." Based on the survey results, the average weighted mean of 5 indicates that end users strongly agree with the system's interface.

Table 10. Admin Evaluation of Interface of the System

Indicators	WM	Interpretation
Question 9	5.00	Strongly Agree
Question 10	5.00	Strongly Agree
Question 11	5.00	Strongly Agree
Question 12	5.00	Strongly Agree
Average Weighted Mean	5.00	Strongly Agree

Table 11 shows respondents' assessments of the usefulness of the developed system. The table displays the weighted mean of responses to questions 14 and 15 which fall into the category of "Strongly Agree," while questions 13, 16, 17, 18, and 19 falls into the category of "Agree." According to the survey results, the average weighted mean of 4.28 indicates that end users generally agree with the system's usefulness.

Table 11. Admin Evaluation of Usefulness of the System

Indicators	WM	Interpretation
Question 13	4.00	Agree
Question 14	5.00	Strongly Agree
Question 15	5.00	Strongly Agree
Question 16	4.00	Agree
Question 17	4.00	Agree
Question 18	4.00	Agree
Question 19	4.00	Agree
Average Weighted Mean	4.28	Agree

Shown in the table 12 are respondents' opinions regarding the ease of use of the developed system. It displays the weighted mean of responses to questions in questionnaires 20 through 27 which all falling into the category of “Strongly Agree.” Based on the survey results, which show an average weighted mean of 5, it can be inferred that end users strongly agree with the ease of use of the system.

Table 12. *Admin Evaluation of Ease of Use of the System*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Wm</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Question 20	5.00	Strongly Agree
Question 21	5.00	Strongly Agree
Question 22	5.00	Strongly Agree
Question 23	5.00	Strongly Agree
Question 24	5.00	Strongly Agree
Question 25	5.00	Strongly Agree
Question 26	5.00	Strongly Agree
Question 27	5.00	Strongly Agree
Average Weighted Mean	5.00	Strongly Agree

Table 13 presents respondents' evaluations of the ease of learning of the developed system by displaying the weighted mean of responses to questions 28, 29, and 30 which all falling into the category of “Strongly Agree,” while question 31 falls into the category of “Agree.” The survey results, with an average weighted mean of 4.75, suggest that end users strongly agree with the ease of learning since the system's design and features facilitate quick comprehension and mastery, making it intuitive and user-friendly.

Table 13. *Admin Evaluation of Ease of Learning of the System*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Question 28	5	Strongly Agree
Question 29	5	Strongly Agree
Question 30	5	Strongly Agree
Question 31	4	Agree
Average Weighted Mean	4.75	Strongly Agree

Depicted in table 14 is the respondents' satisfaction with the developed system. It displays the weighted mean of each question answered by respondents where question 33 falling into the category of “Strongly Agree” and questions 32, 34, 35, and 36 falling into the category of “Agree.” Based on the survey results, which show an average weighted mean of 4.2, it is evident that end users strongly agree with the satisfaction provided by the system.

Table 14. *Admin Evaluation of Satisfaction of the System*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Question 31	4	Agree
Question 32	5	Strongly Agree
Question 33	4	Agree
Question 34	4	Agree
Question 35	4	Agree
Question 36	4	Agree
Average Weighted Mean	4.2	Agree

The overall result from the respondent who serves as admin is shown in Figure 4.26 below. The researcher gave a questionnaire with questions categorized into four: performance/system capabilities, security, ease of use, ease of learning, and satisfaction. Each category got a score called an average weighted mean. performance/system capabilities got 5, which means respondent satisfy with system overall performance and system capabilities. Security got 5, which means people feel safe and trust the security of the system when using it. Ease of use got 5, showing that most people found it really simple to operate and friendly user. Ease of learning got 4.75, indicating that it was not too hard for people to pick up how to use it and easily to catch up with the system activities. Lastly, satisfaction also got 4.20, suggesting that overall, people are quite happy and very satisfied with it. The average score of all the categories earns 4.71, which means that, on average, people are really satisfied with it.

Conclusions

It is evident that the manual process of monitoring vehicles entering and exiting the MSU-LNAC campus poses various challenges, including time consuming, Inaccurate data recording, Delays in providing reports and vulnerable to loss. The development of the MSU-LNAC Web-Based Vehicle Monitoring System offers a promising solution by leveraging QR codes and SMS notifications to automate data collection and improve the recording, monitoring, and reporting of vehicles' entry and exit in the campus. The researchers further conclude that the developed system can help elevate the campus into a technologically advance environment offering a systematized entrance and exit of vehicles.

Based on the findings of the evaluation, which highlighted both strengths and areas for enhancement, several recommendations can be proposed to elevate the functionality and effectiveness of the MSU-LNAC Web-Based Vehicle Monitoring System. These recommendations aim to address identified gaps and capitalize on existing strengths, fostering an even more robust and user-friendly system:

The researchers recommend that the next developers enhance the scanner by integrating it with Android phones for portability.

Improving the normalization of the system's database and implementing features to record the login and logout times of security guards.

Enhancing the restrictions on QR code generation, requiring visitors to obtain confirmation from the system administrator before generating a QR code.

The researchers strongly recommend implementing this system at MSU-LNAC for effective monitoring of individuals entering and exiting the campus. The overall evaluation questionnaire results indicate that users such as students, employees, and community members are satisfied with the system's security, ease of use, ease of learning, and overall satisfaction, with an average weighted mean of 4.93, indicating a "strongly agree" response. Security guards also rate the system highly, with a perfect score of 5 for performance/system capabilities, usefulness, ease of use, ease of learning, and satisfaction. Similarly, administrators are satisfied with the system, achieving an overall average weighted mean of 4.71. These results demonstrate overall satisfaction among respondents with the system.

The researchers recommend implementing an online feedback mechanism which can allow users to provide inputs on their experience with the system and suggestions improvements and inclusion of new features such as AI and GPS for the tracking vehicle improvement of the system through internet.

By implementing these recommendations, the MSU-LNAC Web-Based Vehicle Monitoring System can continue to evolve and meet the evolving needs of its users, ensuring a secure and efficient vehicle monitoring process within the MSU-LNAC campus.

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